

Research Article

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ASSESSMENT OF SOME HEAVY METAL POLLUTANTS IN SMOKED CATFISH (*Clarias gariepinus*) SOLD AT KATUZU AND BAKIN CROSS YAN KIFI GASHUA YOBE STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Fish smoking is the oldest known traditional method of fish processing and preservation. Fish provide the protein needed for bodybuilding and repairs of tissue repair and form part of a healthy, balanced, and nutritious diet. Heavy metal contamination of ingested food substances is a serious health concern due to their high level of toxicological effects on humans. Fish products may become contaminated during processing or due to the intake of heavy metals from a polluted aquatic environment. This research determined the concentration of some heavy metals (Pb, Cr, Cd, and Ni) in smoked Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) sold at Katuzu and Bakin Cross Yan Kifi Gashua Bade Local Government of Yobe State. Smoked fish samples were obtained from two major fish markets in Gashua (Katuzu and Bakin Cross Yan Kifi). The samples were shade-dried for 24hrs and ground into powder. The grounded samples were digested using concentrated nitric acid and hydrogen peroxide (2:1) v/v and analyzed for heavy metals using AAS. The results of the heavy metals concentration (Ni, Cd, Cr, and Pb) of smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) obtained from Bakin Cross were (0.42 ± 0.0037) , (0.61 ± 0.0071) , (1.67 ± 0.0069) , and (0.87 ± 0.0082) mg/kg respectively, While the concentrations of heavy metals obtained from Katuzu were (0.67 ± 0.02558) , (0.81 ± 0.03755) , (2.13 ± 0.01746) , and (1.12 ± 0.04377) mg/kg for Ni, Cd, Cr, and Pb respectively. The results obtained, showed that Cr, and Pd concentrations were above the permissible limits of intake as set by WHO/FAO in both Katuzu and Bakin Cross samples, Cd concentration is within the permissible limit of intake, while Ni concentration from Katuzu exceed the permissible limit and that of Bakin Cross is within the permissible limit. The study recommends a continuous assessment of the level of heavy metals in smoked fish from the study area.

Keywords: Smoked Catfish (*Clarias Gariepinus*); Heavy Metals; Gashua; Atomic Absorption Spectrometer

INTRODUCTION

Fish forms part of a healthy and balanced nutritious diet and provides the needed protein for bodybuilding and repairs of tissue. For many households, fish contains vital micronutrients such as iodine, zinc, iron, and calcium [1]. Fish smoking is the oldest known traditional method of fish processing and preservation [2]. Food commercial handling and processing could increase the level of heavy metal contaminants [3]. as processes such as smoking, drying, frying, roasting, etc reduce the moisture content, thereby increasing the concentration of heavy metals. Processed food substances are also being preserved with chemicals that may contain trace amounts of heavy metals with bioaccumulation potential. Smoked fish samples were reported to have higher concentrations of heavy metals than the fresh samples. Fish has wider acceptability in most parts of Nigeria due to its unique taste, flavor, and good texture. Species such as catfish (*Clarias spp*) are highly accepted and consumed in their smoke-dried form in Nigeria, particularly in Yobe State, due to their affordability and highly delicious flesh. Some natural and human activities

have been a source of heavy metal pollution. Aquatic organisms such as fish and shellfish accumulate metals in their different organs and tissues [4]. At low concentrations, some heavy metals such as copper, cobalt, zinc, iron, and manganese are essential for biological development, which, when consumed, can have potential health consequences [5].

In recent years, the concentrations of toxic metals in many ecosystems have reached unprecedented levels. Under certain environmental conditions, heavy metals may accumulate and cause serious ecological damage. The aquatic ecosystem is often seen as the ultimate recipient of almost everything, including heavy metals [6]. Pollution of heavy metals in the aquatic environment is a growing problem worldwide, and currently it has reached an alarming rate. There are various sources of heavy metals; some originate from anthropogenic activities like the draining of sewage, dumping of hospital wastes, and recreational activities. Conversely, heavy metals also naturally occur in small amounts and may enter the aquatic system through leaching of rocks, airborne dust, forest fires, and vegetation [7].

As heavy metals cannot be degraded, they are continuously being deposited and incorporated into water, sediment, and aquatic organisms [8]. thus, causing heavy metal pollution in water bodies. Heavy metal is any metallic chemical element that has a relatively high density and is toxic or poisonous at low concentrations. Examples of heavy metals include mercury, cadmium, arsenic, chromium, thallium, and lead. As trace elements, some heavy metals (e.g., copper, iron, zinc, manganese, and selenium) are essential to maintain the metabolism of the human body. However, at higher concentrations, they can lead to poisoning [9]. Heavy metals can enter the human food chain through water, air, soil, plants, and animals.

Smoked fish has risen over the last two decades [10]. Smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) consumption is increasingly becoming popular among Nigerians due to its health benefits and its flavour. It is a rich source of protein for the poor and wealthy. Also, smoked catfish may become contaminated during processing or due to the intake of heavy metals from a polluted aquatic environment, as a result of which, it has become increasingly important to determine the concentration of some toxic heavy metals in this fish for consumers' safety.

Fish generally encompass all seafood, including finned fishes, Crustaceans with chitinous exoskeletons such as lobsters, crabs, shrimps, muscle cockles, and oysters. It is a high-protein, low-fat food and an important source of essential nutrients required for supplementing both infants' and adult diets, and provides a range of health benefits. In general, nearly 20% of animal protein sources are provided by fish [11]. and it is a rich source of protein for the poor and wealthy [12]. Fish contains most of the important essential amino acids, particularly lysine, methionine, and tryptophan, that are lacking in plant proteins [13].

Fish has wider acceptability in most parts of Nigeria due to its unique taste, flavour, and good texture. Species such as catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) are highly accepted and consumed in their smoke-dried form in Nigeria, particularly in Yobe State, due to their affordability and highly delicious flesh. Some natural and human activities have been a source of heavy metal pollution. Aquatic organisms such as fish and shellfish accumulate metals in their different organs and tissues [4].

At low concentrations, some heavy metals such as copper, cobalt, zinc, iron, and manganese are essential for biological development, which, when consumed, can have potential health consequences [5]. Furthermore, poor conditions in our local markets, fish handlers, and fish smoking facilities may contribute to the presence of microorganisms in smoked fish. These have led to the persistence of food poisoning, which is an alarming health problem in developing countries where sanitation is low [3].

Fish smoking is the oldest traditional method of fish processing and preservation. Smoked fish such as catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) may become contaminated during processing or due to the intake of heavy metals from a polluted aquatic environment. Heavy metals in ingested food substances are issues of serious health concern due to their high level of toxicological effects on humans [14]. So, there is a need to investigate the heavy metal concentration in smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) sold at Katuzu and Bakin Cross Yan Kifi Gashua.

This study aims to determine the concentration of some heavy metals (Pb, Cr, Cd, and Ni) in smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) sold at Katuzu and Bakin Cross Yan Kifi Gashua using an Atomic Absorbance Spectrophotometer (AAS).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Gashua, situated in Bade local government area of Yobe State, Nigeria, its a geographical coordinate is 12° 52' 5" North and 11° 2' 47" East i.e., it has the latitude 12.8675 and longitude 11.0412 it is a community near Yobe river, a few miles below the convergence of the Hadejia river, is about 299m.

Sample Sources and Collection

The smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) sample was collected from Gashua metropolis, in Bade local government of Yobe State. The fish were collected from two different sampling station: Katuzu Yan Kifi, and Bakin Cross Gashua Yobe State. The catfish from Katuzu was fished at Mashayar Bade River (Amadu reported), and that of Bakin Cross was fished at Bakin Gada River Gashua (Aliyu reported).

Sample Processing

The smoked fish samples obtained from the sampling stations were shade dried, ground into powder, and passed through a sieve number 80 mesh. The samples were then wrapped in a new air-tight polyethylene bag, labeled properly, and transported to

Sample Pre-Treatment/Digestion

1.0g of the sample was weighed into a thoroughly clean digestion vessel (microwave tube), and 6 mL of 65% HNO₃ and 2 mL of H₂O₂ were added and allowed to stand for a while. The digestion vessel (microwave tube) was then covered and placed into the microwave digester (Master 40 serial No: 40G106M) and digested. The digestion was carried out at a temperature of 75 °C for 10 min and then ramped at 100 °C per min to 95 °C and held for 30 min. The digestion was followed by a cooling to room temperature in the microwave [15].

Blanks were used simultaneously in each batch of the analysis to authenticate the analytical quality. The digested samples were diluted with deionized water to a total volume of 100 mL.

Preparation of 1000mg/Liter stock AAS Standard Solution for Selected Elements

The determination of a given metal concentration in the experimental solution was based on its respective calibration curve. In plotting the calibration curves for lead, cadmium, zinc, and other metals, a stock solution of each metal ion of (1000 ppm) supplied by the manufacturer's company was used, from which a standard working solution of 100 ppm was prepared [15].

Standard Working Solution

100 ppm was prepared as a working solution from the 1000 ppm already prepared. A simple dilution formula ($C_1V_1 = C_2V_2$) was used to calculate the volume of the stock solution to be diluted to the new desired concentration. 1 mL of concentrated HNO₃ was added to each working standard and finally diluted to the desired volume with deionized water.

To prepare 100 ppm, 10 mL of the standards and other stock solutions were pipetted and added into 100 mL calibrated flasks, finally diluted with deionized water, and the solution was mixed thoroughly. The other standard working solutions were prepared from 100 ppm by pipetting out an appropriate volume into calibrated flasks and made up to volume with deionized water [15].

Heavy Metals Determination

Determination of Ni, Cd, Cr, and Pb was made directly on each final solution using PerkinElmer AAnalyst 300 Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS).

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using Microsoft Excel. The data were expressed in terms of descriptive statistics, while the figures were presented with mean values as (Mg/Kg).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Concentration of Heavy Metals (Ni, Cd, Cr, Pb) in Smoked Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) from Katuzu

Table 1 shows the heavy metal concentrations in smoked catfish obtained from Katuzu. The mean concentration of Nickel (Ni) in smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) obtained from Katuzu is 0.6703 ± 0.0256 mg/kg, while the WHO/FAO recommended limit for nickel is 0.5 mg/kg. Cadmium (Cd) has a concentration of 0.8070 ± 0.0376 mg/kg, which remains within the permissible limit of 1.0 mg/kg. Chromium (Cr) is present at a significantly higher

concentration of 2.1293 ± 0.0175 mg/kg, compared to the safety threshold of 0.15 mg/kg. Lastly, Lead (Pb) is detected at a concentration of 1.1200 ± 0.0438 mg/kg, exceeding the WHO/FAO limit of 0.2 mg/kg.

Table 1: Mean Concentration of heavy metals (Ni, Cd, Cr, Pb) in smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) obtained from Katuzu

Metals	Concentration(mg/kg)	WHO/FAO (mg/kg)
Nickel (Ni)	0.67 ± 0.0256	0.50
Cadmium (Cd)	0.81 ± 0.0376	1.00
Chromium (Cr)	2.13 ± 0.0175	0.15
Lead (Pb)	1.12 ± 0.0438	0.20

Values of heavy metal concentrations are presented in Mean \pm SD

Concentration of Heavy Metals (Ni, Cd, Cr, Pb) in Smoked Catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) from Bakin Cross Yan Kifi

The mean concentration of Nickel (Ni) in smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) obtained from Bakin Cross Yan kifi is 0.4212 ± 0.00365 mg/kg, which falls below the WHO/FAO limit of 0.5 mg/kg. Cadmium (Cd) is present at a concentration of 0.6072 ± 0.00708 mg/kg, remaining within the permissible limit of 1.0 mg/kg. Chromium (Cr) concentration is measured at 1.6670 ± 0.00694 mg/kg, which significantly exceeds the safety limit of 0.15 mg/kg. Lastly, Lead (Pb) is detected at a concentration of 0.8868 ± 0.00822 mg/kg, surpassing the WHO/FAO recommended limit of 0.2 mg/kg.

Table 2: Mean Concentration of heavy metals (Ni, Cd, Cr, Pb) in smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) obtained from Bakin Cross Yan kifi

Metals	Concentration (mg/kg)	WHO/FAO
Nickel (Ni)	0.42 ± 0.00365	0.50
Cadmium (Cd)	0.61 ± 0.00708	1.00
Chromium (Cr)	1.67 ± 0.00694	0.15
Lead (Pb)	0.89 ± 0.00822	0.20

Values of heavy metal concentrations are presented in Mean \pm SD

DISCUSSION

The results obtained in this study indicate that the mean concentration of Pb in smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) from Katuzu and Bakin Cross are 1.12 and 0.89 mg/kg, respectively. The results when compared with [16]. Regulated standards indicate that both the sample stations are above the set permissible limit (0.2 mg/kg). There is a need for caution in the consumption of smoked fish from Katuzu and Bakin Cross Gashua as they are slightly above the set world permissible limits (0.2 mg/kg) [16].

Ingestion of processed (smoked) fish contaminated with Pb can affect the central nervous system. It is particularly dangerous to babies and children. Pb exposure from contaminated food can result in stunted growth and development, often with the following symptoms: stomach upset, loss of appetite, headaches, sleeping problems, anemia, kidney dysfunction, hearing problems, memory loss, severe abdominal pain, and stumbling when walking [17].

From the results of this study, the mean concentration of Cadmium is 0.8070 and 0.6072 mg/kg in Katuzu and Bakin Cross, respectively. This implies that Cadmium concentration in both samples were below permissible limit of (1.0 mg/kg) standard set by [16]. Cadmium has carcinogenic effects on humans making it to be classified as a human carcinogen [19].

The mean concentrations of Cr were found to be 2.1293mg/kg and 1.6670 mg/kg of smoked catfish (*Clarias garpinus*) from Katuzu and Bakin Cross Gashua, respectively. All were above the permissible limits (0.15 mg/kg) as set by [16]. especially sample from Katuzu with a mean concentration of 2.1293 kg/mg, this study calls for concern because Cr has no known beneficial function in the human system.

Cr from ingested contaminated food can bind to proteins to form complexes that are transported to the kidneys, where they damage the kidneys [17]. Other health effects include: diarrhoea, vomiting, Stomach upset, Fractures in bone, Mutagenicity and carcinogenicity effects, Fertility and teratogenicity, and damage to the nervous and immune systems [3].

The results obtained showed that Ni mean concentrations were 0.6703mg/kg and 0.4212 mg/kg for Katuzu and Bakin Cross, respectively. This indicates that the Katuzu Smoked catfish exceeds the permissible limit (0.50 kg/mg), and the sample of Bakin Cross is below the permissible limit set by [16]. This implies that either smoking or the use of additives (preservatives) on the smoked fish may have contributed to the increase in the concentration of Ni on the smoked fish. [8]. suggested that smoking may increase the level of concentration of heavy metals in the smoked fish. Ni is transported in the blood and is reported to accumulate in the liver and kidneys. It poses a great toxic effect on the human kidney, the respiratory and skeletal systems.

CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the concentrations of heavy metals—Nickel (Ni), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), and Lead (Pb)—in smoked catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) from two locations, Katuzu and Bakin Cross Yan kifi, and compared them with WHO/FAO permissible limits for food safety. The results indicate that while Cadmium levels in both locations were within acceptable limits, the concentrations of Nickel, Chromium, and Lead exceeded these thresholds, with Chromium and Lead showing significantly high levels. These findings raise critical concerns regarding the safety of smoked catfish from these locations, as the elevated levels of these toxic metals pose potential health risks, including carcinogenic, neurological, and developmental effects. To ensure consumer safety, it is imperative to implement strategies aimed at reducing heavy metal contamination in aquatic ecosystems and fish products. This includes regular monitoring of water quality, adherence to proper smoking and handling practices, and community awareness campaigns on the sources and effects of heavy metals. The study underscores the importance of continued research into heavy metal contamination in food sources, providing valuable insights for policymakers and health authorities to safeguard public health.

REFERENCES

1. Forsberg ND, Wilson GR, Anderson KA. Determination of Parent and Substituted Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons in High-Fat Salmon Using a Modified QuEChERS Extraction, Dispersive SPE and GC–MS. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*. 2012;59(15), 8108-8116.
2. Hokkanen M, Luhtasela U, Kostamo P, Ritvanen T, Peltonen K, Jestoi M. Critical Effects of Smoking Parameters on the Levels of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons in Traditionally Smoked Fish and Meat Products in Finland. *Journal of Chemistry*. 2018; Article ID 2160958, 14 pages.
3. Igwegbe AO, Negbenebor CA, Chibuzo EC, Badau MH, Agbara GI. Effects of Season and Fish Smoking on Heavy Metal Contents of Selected Fish Species from Three Locations in Borno State of Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Science and Technology*. 2015;6(2), 1010-1019.
4. Amos-Tautua B, Inengite A, Abasi C, Amirize G. Evaluation of Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons and Some Heavy Metals in Roasted Food Snacks in Amassoma, Niger Delta, Nigeria. *African Journal of Environmental Science and Technology*. 2013;7(10), 961-966.
5. Ismaniza I, Mat S. Analysis of Heavy Metals in Water and Fish (*Tilapia sp*) Samples from Tasik Mutiara, Puchong. *Malaysian Journal of Analytical Sciences*. 2012;16(3), 346-352.
6. Ogoyi DO, Mwitab CJ, Nguu EK, Shiundu PM. Determination of Heavy Metals Content in Water, Sediment, and Microalgae from Lake Victoria, East Africa. *The Open Environmental Engineering Journal*. 2011;4, 156-161.
7. Fernandez-Leborans G, Olalla-Herrero Y. Toxicity and Bioaccumulation of Lead and Cadmium in Marine Protozoa Communities. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety*. 2000;47, 266-276.
8. Linnik PM, Zubenko IB. Secondary Pollution of Aquatic Environments by Heavy Metals Compounds. *Lakes and Reservoirs: Research and Management*. 2000;5(1), 11-21.
9. Lennetech. Heavy metals. Retrieved June 13, 2014 from <http://www.lennetech.com/processes/heavy/heavy-metals/heavy-metals.htm>.
10. Akinsorotan AM, Jimoh JO, Omobepade BP, Adene ID. Status of Trace Metals in Smoked *Clarias gariepinus* Cultured in Earthen Pond in Lagos State, Nigeria. *3rd International Conference on Science and Sustainable Developments*. 2019.

11. Oladejo AJ. Economic Analysis of Small-Scale Catfish Farming in Ido Local Government Area of Oyo State, Nigeria. *Agricultural Journal*. 2010;5, 318-321.
12. Abdullahi AS, Abolude DS, Ega RA. Nutrient Quality of Four Oven-Dried Freshwater Catfish in Northern Nigeria. *Journal of Tropical Bioscience*. 2001;3, 70-75.
13. Onyia LU, Adebayo EF, Adewuyi KO, Ekwunife EG, Ochokwu IJ. Comparative Economics of Fresh and Smoked Fish Marketing in Some Local Government Areas in Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Australia Conference Proceedings*. 2014;IIFET.
14. Mathias NB, Tijjani SI, Idris UZ. Determination of Heavy Metals Contamination on Smoked Fish Sold at Some Fish Markets in Borno State. *Journal of Chemical Health Risks*. 2023;13(1):135-143.
15. AOAC International. Official Method 2015.01: Heavy Metals in Food - Microwave Digestion and Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES). *Journal of AOAC International*. 2015.
16. WHO/FAO. World Health Organization/Food and Agriculture Organization, Codex Alimentarius Commission, General Standard for Contaminants and Toxins in Food and Feed. *Codex Alimentarius Commission Standards*. 2015; CODEX STAN 193-1995.
17. Jan AT, Azam M, Siddiqui K, Ali A, Choi I, Haq QMR. Heavy Metals and Human Health: Mechanistic Insight into Toxicity and Counter Defense +System of Antioxidants. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 2015;16(12):29592-29630.
18. Oloruntoba A, Oloruntoba AP, Oluwaseun AR. Determination of Heavy Metal Levels in Green Pea (*Pisum sativum*): A Case Study of Selected Markets in Abuja, FCT. *American Journal of Innovative Research and Applied Sciences*. 2017;5(5), 343-349.
19. Ali AS, US SA, Ahmad R. Effect of Different Heavy Metal Pollution on Fish. *Research Journal of Chemistry and Environmental Sciences*. 2014;2(1), 74-79.